

LOOKING AT THE ACTIVITIES OF CULTURAL CENTERS: PROVIDING CULTURAL CENTERS WITH QUALIFIED STAFF

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ABSTRACT

The article describes in detail the role of cultural centers in our lives, their activities, tasks, as well as the opportunities and conditions created to bring our centers to a new level, the issues of attracting qualified personnel to cultural centers. Suggestions and comments were made on the issues that need to be addressed in order to expand the activities of cultural and art institutions, to promote our national culture among the population, to organize meaningful leisure time for young people, to strengthen the attention of our people to our culture and art. The relationship between the staff and the manager at the centers describes the need to approach problems with modern methods and innovative ideas.

Keywords: culture, art, cultural center, spirituality, creative team, staff, specialist.

The sphere of culture and art is to create works of art that reflect the spiritual image of our people, their way of life, in a word, to express their identity, to improve the quality of services provided by cultural and art institutions. is based on, most importantly, an area that works with people. By the way, as the President said, "We must never forget one truth, if culture and art do not develop in our country, society will not develop." [1:23] , there is an integrated system for the widespread promotion of our customs and traditions. The role of cultural and art institutions under the Ministry of Culture, including theaters, circuses, art palaces, libraries, parks and cultural centers, is invaluable. In particular, cultural centers play an important role in the development of society and the spiritual development of young people, as well as the meaningful use of their leisure time. We can say that the society will definitely

develop sustainably if all the 826 Cultural Centers that are currently operating fulfill the following main tasks. Including,

- Improving the quality of cultural services to the population, meeting their cultural needs and ensuring a meaningful leisure time, the formation of exemplary programs of creative communities that embody national values, customs and traditions;

- Preservation and development of folk art and amateur art, the creation of favorable conditions for the formation and operation of artistic and practical creative communities, amateur groups and the systematic enrichment of the creative process;

- Involvement of children in clubs, study of foreign languages and the organization of courses on "speech culture", the widespread promotion of all genres and directions of folk art, amateur art and intangible cultural heritage and their originality. to pass on to the next generation;

- Organizing spiritual, educational, cultural and public events with literary and artistic figures and professional creative groups, holding direct artistic meetings and roundtables with the population, especially young people;

- holding competitions, district (city) festivals of folk art and performing arts, identification of talented youth, support of creative youth;

- organization of public holidays, performances and folk festivals, provision of paid services to legal entities and individuals in the socio-cultural sphere;

- organization of various clubs, studios, courses, hobby clubs, amateur art groups.

[2: 69.70] Of course, there is a need for qualified specialists who can effectively perform the above-mentioned tasks and increase the capacity of cultural centers. The Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture and its branches train and bring up the best personnel who fully organize the activities of cultural centers. It serves as a "factory" that trains professionals in all areas of culture and the arts. Today, about 1,500 students study at the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture and its branches in the field of culture and arts management. As a result of the attention paid to the field of culture and art in our country, in 10 regional state universities of the republic in each course (currently there are 3 courses in total) 25 students are trained in the newly established "Organization and management of cultural and art institutions." They are studying in the direction of The President admitted 5 students from each district to the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture and its branches at the expense of the local budget for the education of talented young people in the field of culture and arts. We can see that more than 2,000 students are studying in the field of culture and art administration across the country. But the staffing issue still remains topical. Frankly, most of our graduates do not go to the cultural center in their region or district. This is also affected by the unsatisfactory salaries in our cultural centers. The main goals of our students,

who have not yet graduated from the institute, are "I will work in another lucrative field, earning an average of 1 million 300-1 million 400 thousand a month", "I am studying for a second specialty", "I will do business". As the inventor Henry Ford put it, "If you don't get paid, you get paid." Therefore, the heads of each regional and district department of culture of the republic should work in cooperation with these educational institutions. Heads of departments who have been working directly with the student for 4 years through the institute will have the opportunity to provide the cultural centers with highly qualified staff. In addition, sending students to internships in cultural centers in their districts, studying the activities and organizational structures of the centers at a lower level on the example of their districts, leads to effective results. One aspect of the analysis of these works is very complex, but the other aspect is a very interesting process. Because culture and art have always been in the focus of our state. In this regard, President Sh. Mirziyoyev said: "Speaking of social reforms, strengthening the material and technical base of such areas as science, education, health, culture and art, media, physical culture and sports, It should be noted that the issues of human resource development have been in the center of our attention for the last 5 years." [3: 137] In particular, I am studying at the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture as a future manager of culture and arts. Our industry is rising to the level of state policy, and the doors of wide opportunities are opening. Of course, we should be able to answer workably. Today, the activities of cultural centers, in general, the expansion of cultural and art institutions, the promotion of our national culture among the population, the meaningful organization of youth leisure, strengthening the attention of our people to our culture and art and full involvement of public policy. By the way, the United States does not have state-run cultural centers, palaces of culture, libraries, theaters, museums, and parks, as in our country. This does not mean that there are no cultural institutions in the United States. Not only in the United States, but in many foreign countries as well. There are cultural and social services in every locality. They do not require funds from the state budget, they are built and managed by the people themselves. [4:59] You see, all our cultural and art institutions are in the hands of the state, all the opportunities are given to the state. Can we make the most of it? The response of our people to the changes is not enough. Views on culture as a concert, a spectacle, are not over. In my opinion, the word culture has become easier to understand. Unfortunately, today the status of cultural centers and representatives of the cultural sphere working in them is not highly valued among our people. It is disappointing that people living in remote areas of the country still consider an artist an "artist" or a "shepherd", our dancers a "player", and a "middleman" a master of

words. Culture is not just a luxury or a wedding, but culture is a mirror of our people. Therefore, we, the representatives of culture and art, need to take the locomotive.

Today, the heads of cultural centers are instructed to conduct cultural and educational work among the population, to develop and monitor the implementation of the main directions of meaningful organization of leisure time, to organize activities in accordance with the Charter of the center, to provide the center with qualified personnel. implementation, development of creative-production and financial-economic activity plans, proper distribution of funds, signing of economic contracts and financial documents, hiring and dismissal, issuance of orders and directives within its competence, labor protection, safety and fire safety measures control over compliance, cooperation with public authorities, local and foreign organizations, the formation of amateur creative groups, the organization of work to improve the skills of staff, the activities of the center A number of priorities have been set, such as maintaining outgoing (paid services) accounts and submitting reports on time. Are the leaders of the cultural center performing these functions? We cannot answer this question in the affirmative, unfortunately. First of all, the head of the center must be able to understand and control his subordinates in terms of humanity, and most importantly, to be a role model for the management staff. To do this, of course, it is necessary to have a highly educated practitioner in the field who meets the qualification requirements, correctly assesses the problems, has a long-term vision and knows a foreign language. When the manager is able to perform the task assigned to him / her, he / she will achieve the desired result. Lack of knowledge of foreign languages by many center directors is a major obstacle to bringing cultural centers up to date. For this reason, the requirements for teaching in the field of "Organization and management of cultural and artistic institutions" at our institute require a perfect knowledge of at least one foreign language and the creation of conditions for this.

Today, life requires new thinking and work, the formation of our national "centers of intelligence." [5: 271]. Therefore, the staff of cultural centers requires a lot of responsibility and dedication. In the new Uzbekistan, cultural centers should play the role of the greatest force for the dissemination of culture and art among the people.

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